

Synthesis of some new N^1 -[(2-oxo-3-chloro-4-aryl-azetidino)-(acetyl amino)]-indole derivatives and their pharmacological activity

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Manuscript received 17 March 2006, revised 25 July 2006, accepted 7 September 2006

Abstract : Indole on reaction with chloroacetyl chloride afforded N^1 -(1-chloro acetyl)-indole which was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate to give N^1 -[(1-hydrazino)acetyl]-indole. The hydrazino derivative of indole was further treated with various substituted aromatic carbonyls to get N^1 -[(benzylidene hydrazino)-acetyl]-indoles (3a-j). The compounds 3a-j were treated with chloroacetyl chloride in presence of Et_3N to afford N^1 -[(2-oxo-3-chloro-4-aryl-azetidino)-(acetyl amino)]-indoles, 4a-j. The structures of all the compounds were elucidated by elemental analysis, IR and ^1H NMR spectrometry. All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and anticonvulsant activities.

Keywords : Synthesis, pharmacological activity, indole.

1H-Indole derivatives possess various pharmacological activity¹. 2-Azetidinone derivatives are currently useful in the formation of various drugs for the treatment of various microbial diseases². In this paper, we have reported synthesis of some new 1H-indole derivatives attached with 2-oxoazetidino ring and evaluated their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and anticonvulsant activities.

Results and discussion

The required starting material N^1 -(1-chloroacetyl)-indole **1** was prepared by treatment of equimolar solution of indole and chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethylamine. Compound **1** was treated with hydrazine hydrate in methanol to get N^1 -[(1-hydrazino) acetyl]-indole, **2**. The hydrazino derivatives, was condensed with various selected aromatic carbonyls to yield N^1 -[(benzylidene hydrazino)-acetyl]-indoles (**3a-j**). The final products N^1 -[(2-oxo-3-chloro-4-aryl-azetidino)-(acetyl amino)]-indoles (**4a-j**) were synthesized by cycloaddition of the compounds **3a-j** by chloroacetyl chloride in presence of triethyl amine (Scheme 1). Purity of all new synthesized compound was monitored by silica gel G coated TLC plates.

Compounds **3a-j** and **4a-j** were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Escherchia coli* (*Ec*), *Strepto-*

coccus aureus (*Sa*) and *Shigella dysenteriae* (*Sd*) and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* (*An*), *Candida albicans* (*Ca*) and *Rizopus oryzae* (*Ro*) at 50 and 100 ppm concentrations by filter paper disc technique³ (Table 1). Antibacterial streptomycin and antifungal griseofulvin were used as standard drugs under similar conditions for comparison. The following compounds were found active against the tested bacteria : **3d** (*Ec*, *Sa*, *Sd*), **3g** (*Sd*), **3h** (*Ec*), **4d** (*Ec*, *Sa*, *Sd*), **4h** (*Sa*) and active against the following fungi : **3d** (*An*, *Ca*, *Ro*), **3g** (*Ca*, *Ro*), **3h** (*An*, *Ro*), **3j** (*Ro*), **4a** (*Ro*), **4b** (*Ro*), **4c** (*An*), **4d** (*An*, *Ca*, *Ro*), **4g** (*An*), **4h** (*Ro*) (Table 2).

Compounds **3a-j** and **4a-j** were also screened for their anti-inflammatory activity by carrageenan induced rat paw oedema method⁴ at a dose of 50 mg/kg bw in albino rats (weighing 70-115 g). The rat paw oedema was produced by the method of Winter *et al.*⁴. The percent inhibition of inflammation was calculated by applying Newbold formula⁴. The following compounds were found to exhibit anti-inflammatory activity : **3b** (30%), **3c** (30%), **3d** (36.66%), **3e** (40%), **3g** (36.66%), **3h** (40%), **4d** (33.3%), **4g** (30%) and **4h** (40%) as compared to phenylbutazone (46.66%) (Table 3).

Compounds **3a-j** and **4a-j** (100 mg/kg bw) were also screened for their anticonvulsant activity against

Compd.	R	Ar
3, 4b	H	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4c	H	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4d	H	2-Br-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4e	H	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4f	H	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4g	CH ₃	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4h	CH ₃	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4i	CH ₃	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄
3, 4j	CH ₃	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) ClCH₂COCl, (ii) NH₂NH₂, (iii) RCOAr, (iv) ClCH₂COCl.

pentylene-tetrazole (90 mg/kg bw) induced convulsions in albino rats (30–40 g) of either sex by the reported method⁵. Phenobarbitone was used as a reference drug at 50 mg/kg bw, which was observed to protect 100% against the induced convulsions. Compounds **3c**, **3d**, **3g**, **3h**, **4c**, **4d**, **4g** and **4h** provided 60, 70, 60, 60, 60, 80, 60 and 60% protection (Table 3).

These pharmacological results clearly demonstrate that chloro and bromo derivatives enhanced the biological activity as compared to other groups.

Experimental

M.p.s. were obtained in an open capillary tube. Structures of all the compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral data. The IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 in CDCl₃ at (200 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. The homogeneity of all the compounds were verified on silica gel G coated TLC plates and the spots were located by iodine vapours.

N^1 -(1-Chloro acetyl)-indole (1) :

The equimolar solution of indole (0.1 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.1 mol) in presence of triethyl amine (0.2 mol) and methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for about 15 h and cooled. The product was filtered and dried. The product was recrystallized from chloroform, yield (73%), m.p. 102 °C (Found : C, 61.93; H, 4.01; N, 7.25. C₁₀H₈NOCl calcd. : C, 62.01; H, 4.13; N, 7.23%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3342, 3240, 3070, 2950, 2854, 1607, 1317 and 1254 (indole nucleus), 2878 (C-CH₂), 2270, 2242 and 1783 (>N-C=O) and 761 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl);

Table 1. Antibacterial screening results of the compounds 3a-j and 4a-j

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		<i>S. dysenteriae</i>	
	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm
3a	+	++	+	++	-	-
3b	+	++	-	+	+	+
3c	+	++	+	++	++	++
3d	+++	+++	+++	++++	++	+++
3e	+	++	-	+	+	++
3f	-	+	-	+	+	++
3g	+	++	+	+	++	+++
3h	++	+++	+	++	+	++
3i	+	++	-	+	-	+
3j	+	++	+	++	-	+
4a	+	++	+	++	+	++

Table-1 (contd.)

4b	+	++	-	++	-	-
4c	+	++	+	++	+	+
4d	++	+++	++	+++	++	+++
4e	-	+	-	+	-	+
4f	-	+	-	-	-	+
4g	+	++	+	++	-	+
4h	+	++	++	+++	-	+
4i	-	+	-	+	-	+
4j	-	+	+	++	-	-
SM	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

SM = Streptomycin, inhibition diameter in mm. (-) 5-7; (+) 7-12; (++) 12-18; (+++) 18-24; (++++) 24-30.

Table 2. Antifungal screening results of the compounds 3a-j and 4a-j

Compd.	<i>A. niger</i>		<i>C. albicans</i>		<i>R. oryzae</i>	
	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm
3a	-	+	-	+	-	-
3b	+	++	-	+	-	+
3c	-	+	++	++	+	++
3d	+++	++++	+++	+++	++	+++
3e	+	++	-	-	-	-
3f	-	+	-	+	+	++
3g	+	++	+++	+++	++	+++
3h	++	+++	-	+	++	+++
3i	+	++	-	+	-	-
3j	+	+	+	+	++	+++
4a	-	+	+	-	++	+++
4b	++	++	+	+	+	+++
4c	++	+++	++	++	+	++
4d	++	+++	+++	++++	+++	++++
4e	-	+	+	++	-	+
4f	-	-	-	+	-	-
4g	++	+++	-	+	+	++
4h	-	++	+	++	++	+++
4i	-	+	-	+	-	-
4j	++	++	-	+	-	-
GF	+++	++++	+++	++++	+++	++++

GF= Griseofulvin, inhibition diameter in mm : (-) 4-8; (+) 8-12; (++) 12-16; (+++) 16-23; (++++) 23-29.

Table 3. Antiinflammatory and anticonvulsant screening results of the compounds 3a-j and 4a-j (does 50/100 mg/kg)

Compd.	Antiinflammatory			Anticonvulsant percentage	
	Before carrageen administration	Paw volume after 5 h	Percent inhibition	Protection	Mortality
3a	0.67 ± 0.03	0.22 ± 0.02	26.66	40	10
3b	0.70 ± 0.02	0.21 ± 0.03	30.00	50	10
3c	0.72 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.02	30.00	60	10
3d	0.72 ± 0.02	0.18 ± 0.02	36.66	70	10

Table-3 (contd.)

3e	0.76 ± 0.02	0.20 ± 0.03	40.00	40	10
3f	0.68 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.02	16.66	50	20
3g	0.73 ± 0.03	0.19 ± 0.03	36.66	60	10
3h	0.75 ± 0.02	0.19 ± 0.02	40.00	60	10
3i	0.73 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.03	3.33	40	20
3j	0.63 ± 0.03	0.25 ± 0.02	16.66	20	10
4a	0.66 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02	20.00	40	10
4b	0.69 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.03	26.66	50	10
4c	0.70 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.03	23.33	60	20
4d	0.73 ± 0.04	0.24 ± 0.02	33.33	80	10
4e	0.68 ± 0.03	0.23 ± 0.02	23.33	50	10
4f	0.67 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02	20.00	40	20
4g	0.72 ± 0.03	0.21 ± 0.02	30.00	60	20
4h	0.74 ± 0.03	0.20 ± 0.02	40.00	60	20
4i	0.67 ± 0.02	0.25 ± 0.02	16.66	40	10
4j	0.69 ± 0.03	0.26 ± 0.02	13.33	40	10
Control	0.66 ± 0.03	0.30 ± 0.01	-	-	-
PB	0.69 ± 0.02	0.16 ± 0.01	46.66	100	-

PB = Phenylbutazone standard drug/Phenobarbitone.

Table 4. Physical and spectral data of the compounds 3a-j and 4a-j

Compd.	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	NMR (δ)
3b	80	120	3423, 3442 and 2885 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2272, 2242 and 1793 (>N-C=O), 1543 (N=CH) and 765 (C-Cl)	4.42 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.95 (1H, s, N=CII), 6.32-7.31 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.71 (1H, s, NH)
3c	75	130	3425, 3342 and 2883 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2278, 2241 and 1795 (>N-C=O), 765 (C-Cl) and 1544 (N=CH)	4.42 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.95 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.32-7.33 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.76 (1H, s, NH)
3d	73	132	3431, 3344 and 2880 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2275, 2251 and 1789 (>N-C=O), 1545 (N=CH) and 615 (C-Br)	4.44 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.95 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.33-7.37 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.76 (1H, s, NH)
3e	84	142	3432, 3351 and 2883 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2276, 2243 and 1780 (N-C=O) and 1546 (N=CH)	4.42 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.92 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.31-7.33 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.81 (1H, s, NH)
3f	79	139	3433, 3352 and 2883 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2276, 2243 and 1782 (N-C=O) and 1545 (N=CH)	4.44 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 4.93 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.31-7.35 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.85 (1H, s, NH)
3g	82	135	2925, 1473, 1373 (N-C-CH ₃), 2278, 2247, 1788 (N-C=O) and 767 (C-Cl)	1.15 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 4.46 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 6.34-7.36 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
3h	74	109	2928, 1473, 1375 (N-C-CH ₃), 2278, 2247, 1788 (N-C=O) and 767 (C-Cl)	1.16 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 4.45 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 6.35-7.36 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
3i	87	136	3421, 3343, 2886 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2923, 1474, 1373 (N-C-CH ₃) and 2273, 2243, 1786 (N-C=O)	1.14 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 4.47 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 6.32-7.41 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.83 (1H, s, NH)

3j	80	143	3422, 3343, 2886 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2925, 1475, 1373 (N-C-CH ₃) and 2274, 2243, 1786 (N-C=O)	1.15 (3H, s, N-C-CH ₃), 4.47 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 6.32-7.41 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.83 (1H, s, NH)
4b	89	149	3430, 3346, 2882 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2274, 2248, 1784 (N-C=O) and 756 (C-Cl)	3.19 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-4), 4.42 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.52 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 5.56-7.39 (1H, m, Ar-H) and 7.76 (1H, s, NH)
4c	78	103	3435, 3344, 2882 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2273, 2248, 1785 (N-C=O) and 755 (C-Cl)	3.19 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-4), 4.45 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.54 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 5.56-7.39 (1H, m, Ar-H) and 7.76 (s, 1H, NH)
4d	73	145	3427, 3343, 2882 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2273, 2244, 1736 (N-C=O), 786 (C-Cl) and 615 (C-Br)	3.18 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-4), 4.44 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.52-7.39 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.30-7.36 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
4e	74	138	3431, 3344, 2886 (-CH ₂ -NH), 3389 (C-OH aromatic), 2275, 2243, 1786 (N-C=O) and 762 (C-Cl)	3.16 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-4), 4.43 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.53 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.28-7.37 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
4f	80	143	3433, 3345, 2885 (-CH ₂ -NH), 3389 (C-OH aromatic), 2276, 2245, 1785 (N-C=O) and 762 (C-Cl)	3.15 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-4), 4.45 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.54 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.28-7.37 (m, 10H, Ar-H) and 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
4g	74	110	3424, 3348, 2887 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2927, 1472, 1377 (N-C-CH ₃) and 757 (C-Cl)	1.19 (3H, s, C-4), 4.43 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.51 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.31-7.33 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.73 (1H, s, NH)
4h	70	115	3425, 3346, 2888 (-CH ₂ -NH), 2925, 1472, 1376 (N-C-CH ₃) and 758(C-Cl)	1.17 (3H, s, C-4), 4.44 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.52 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.33-7.35 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.75 (1H, s, NH)
4i	78	124	3433, 3347, 2889 (-CH ₂ -NH), 3385 (C-OH aromatic), 2926, 1475, 1376 (N-C-CH ₃) and 765 (C-Cl)	1.19 (3H, s, C-4), 4.45 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.54 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.86-7.39 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.70 (1H, s, NH)
4j	76	118	3435, 3348, 2888 (-CH ₂ -NH), 3380 (C-OH aromatic), 2925, 1472, 1375 (N-C-CH ₃) and 763 (C-Cl)	1.16 (3H, s, C-4), 4.43 (2H, s, -CH ₂), 5.55 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.87-7.39 (10H, m, Ar-H) and 7.75 (1H, s, NH)

δ 4.43 (2H, s, -CH₂) and 6.30-7.20 (6H, m, Ar-H).

*N*¹-[(1-Hydrazino)acetyl]-indole (2) :

A mixture of the compound 1 (0.06 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.06 mol) in methanol (40 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for about 7 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the product was recrystallized from methanol, yield (76%), m.p. 105 °C (Found : C, 63.45; H, 5.77; N, 22.20. C₁₀H₁₁N₃O calcd. : C, 63.49; H, 5.82; N, 22.22%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3344 cm⁻¹ (-NHNH₂); δ 4.39 (2H, s, -CH₂), 4.56 (2H, s, -NH₂), 6.63-7.52 (6H, m, Ar-H) and 7.89 (1H, s, -NH).

*N*¹-[(Benzylidene hydrazino)-acetyl]-indole (3a) :

The compound 2 (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01

mol) with 4-5 drops of glacial acetic acid were refluxed in methanol (30 ml) on a water bath for about 8 h. It was cooled, concentrated and filtered. The product was recrystallized from chloroform : ethanol mixture, yield (82%), m.p. 106 °C (Found : C, 73.60; H, 5.37; N, 15.10. C₁₇H₁₅N₃O calcd. : C, 73.64; H, 5.41; N, 15.16 %); $\nu_{\max}$ 3427, 3441, 2883 (-CH₂-NH), 1543 cm⁻¹ (-N=CH); δ 4.48 (2H, s, -CH₂), 4.93 (1H, s, -N=CH), 6.30-7.70 (11H, m, Ar-H) and 7.71 (1H, s, -NH).

Other compounds 3b-j were synthesized in a similar manner using various selected aromatic carbonyls.

*N*¹-[(2-Oxo-3-chloro-4-aryl-azitiidin)-(acetyl amino)]-indole (4a) :

The compound 3a (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.02

mol) in dioxane (30 ml) was first stirred for about 6 h followed by the refluxation with chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) on a water bath for about 5 h and cooled. The solid thus obtained was filtered and dried. The separated product was recrystallized from ethanol, yield (80%), m.p. 137 °C (Found : C, 58.70; H, 3.82; N, 10.78. $C_{19}H_{16}N_3O_2Cl$ calcd. : C, 58.76; H, 3.86; N, 10.82%); ν_{max} 2276, 2244, 1783 ($>N-C=O$), 763 cm^{-1} (C-Cl); δ 3.17 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-4), 4.43 (2H, s, $-CH_2$), 5.51 (1H, d, J 5 Hz, C-3), 6.34–7.43 (11H, m, Ar-H) and 7.74 (1H, s, -NH).

Other compounds **4b-j** were synthesized from **3a-j** in a similar manner (Table 4).¹

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head, SAIF, CDRI, Luknow for providing the elemental analysis and spectral data of the synthesized compounds. We are also grateful to the Head, Department of Botany and Chemistry of this University for providing antimicrobial and experimental facility.

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